

D3.2 Report on initial AI algorithm development

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Althena concept and approach

Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions have emerged thanks to novel Artificial Intelligence (AI) which can be trained with huge amounts of data to produce driving functions with better-than-human performance under certain conditions. The race on AI continues to build hardware (HW) and software (SW) frameworks to manage and process even larger real and synthetic datasets to train increasingly accurate AI models. However, AI remains largely unexplored with respect to explainability (interpretability of model functioning), privacy preservation (exposure of sensitive data), ethics (bias and wanted/unwanted behaviour), and accountability (responsibilities of AI outputs). These features will establish the basis of trustworthy AI as a novel paradigm to fully understand and trust AI in operation, while using it at its full capabilities for the benefit of society. Althena will contribute to build Explainable AI (XAI) in CCAM development and testing frameworks, researching three main AI pillars: data (real/synthetic data management), models (data fusion, hybrid AI approaches), and testing (physical/virtual X-in-the-loop (XiL) set-ups with scalable Machine Learning Operations (MLOps)). A human-centric methodology will be created to derive trustworthy AI dimensions from user identified group needs in CCAM applications. Althena will innovate by proposing a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) on XAI and an analysis to explore trade-offs between these dimensions. Demonstrators will show the Althena methodology in four critical use cases: perception (what does the AI perceive, and why), situational awareness (what is the AI understanding about the current driving environment, including the driver state), decision (why a certain decision is taken), and traffic management (how transport-level applications interoperate with AI-enabled systems operating at vehicle level). Created data and tools will be made available via European data sharing initiatives (OpenData and OpenTools) to foster research on trustworthy AI for CCAM.

1.2 Purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable D3.2 is the second output of WP3 (model development) and is related to all tasks of WP3. This deliverable focuses on reporting the first initial designs of the AI algorithms that are being developed within AITHENA, according to the AITHENA pipeline. This report covers the initial AI algorithm developments including their initial feature validation according to the specified requirements and specifications.

Simultaneously, some of the results of these algorithms are being reported in deliverable D5.2 [1]. Where necessary, we have indicated a brief result in this deliverable and provided references to D5.2.

This deliverable also incorporates further developments using the AITHENA ML Framework that was already published in D3.1. As mentioned in D3.1, the results of Task 3.1 will be embedded in D3.2 and D3.3.

This deliverable provides a first iteration towards achieving the following general objectives of Althena:

- XAI - GO-2: XAI models – research and development of explainable AI models,
- DATA - GO-5: Development Framework (“DevOps” like) to ensure data and model lifecycle tracking and management,

- DATA - GO-6: Digital Twin for data generation,
- TEST - GO-7: Testing and validation procedures – methodology for extending HEADSTART methodology to include AI based functions and systems,
- CCAM - SO-1: Trustworthy and Robust Perception systems,
- CCAM - SO-2: Human Understandable Situation Awareness System including driver state,
- CCAM – SO-3: Explainable Driving Decision methods.

1.3 Structure of this deliverable

According to the grant agreement, tasks 3.2, 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5 focus on the different parts of the perception, situation awareness / understanding and decision-making pipeline as present in the following architecture:

Figure 1: AITHENA architecture, with relationship of tasks T3.2, T3.3, T3.4 and T3.5 integrated.

All the AI algorithms that are being developed in Athena are developed in these 4 tasks. Additionally, task 3.1 provides the machine learning life-cycle management framework. Figure 2 provides an overview of how WP3 tasks fit together, how WP1 and WP2 provide input to WP3, and how WP4 and WP5 are interacting (both ways) with WP3.

WP1 and T2.2 provide input with the requirements and ML DevOps data governance structure to task 3.1 which provided an overview of a ML life-cycle management framework.

In parallel the four tasks T3.2 – T3.5 focus on the individual parts as described in Figure 1 already above.

In WP4 the tools for the development and testing of the AI algorithms are developed and in WP5 the testing methodology and UC requirements are defined.

Specifically, D5.2 has a direct link to this deliverable, as evaluation results of several AI algorithms described in this deliverable are being described in full detail there. D3.2 focuses therefore more on the initial description and methodologies used for developing these AI algorithms, with only a minor initial result.

Figure 2: structure of WP3 with respect to other work packages and use cases

This deliverable is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 provides a short update on the ML Framework (T3.1) that was previously introduced in D3.1. Since this task only had one deliverable while the framework remained in continuous development, we provide an update in this deliverable.

Chapter 3 focuses on the data and information fusion to reduce conflicting perception (linked to work in T3.2).

Chapter 4 focuses on the transparent edge-case training using mixed real-synthetic data (linked to the work in T3.3) and on safety-critical and trustworthy predictive models (linked to the work in T3.4).

Chapter 5 focuses on explainable and robust decision making (manoeuvre and trajectory) (linked to the work in T3.5)

Chapter 6 provides a conclusion and outlook towards D3.3 (which is the update of this deliverable).

2 ML DEVELOPMENT AND LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

In the previous deliverable 3.1. Life-cycle management framework for ML models [2], a description of the ML (machine learning) development cycle has been presented. A special contribution was the definition of a model and MLOps (Machine Learning Operations) card. These tools not only promote transparency but also encourage standardization for reporting relevant information to different potential users.

Our defined model card proposes a series of sections inspired by Mitchell et al.'s [3] original model card concept, with the addition and reordering of some sections to include ML developments within the CCAM field. In alignment with Althena's human-centric design, the model card is complemented by a checklist. This assists developers or creators in providing pertinent details about their model or system, ensuring that comprehensive and relevant information is shared.

Since the publication of D3.1 [2], led by Vicomtech, and the preparation of the current document, new ideas for improvements to the model card model have emerged. We have identified potential improvements, particularly focusing on developments related to the CCAM field and compatibility with the recently proposed EU AI Act [4] and the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) [5]. These enhancements aim to ensure that our model card remains a robust, relevant, and effective tool in the rapidly evolving landscape of machine learning.

2.2 Updates with respect to D3.1

Since the model cards advocate for contributing to the transparency of an AI system, it was prudent to examine existing legislation and guidelines for trustworthy AI and see what they say or require regarding transparency. This is particularly convenient for requirements that can fit or are related to CCAM.

The ALTAI defines seven key requirements for Trustworthy AI and defines transparency as including traceability, explainability, and open communication about an AI system's limitations. The AI Act does not provide a precise definition of transparency. Still, it states that high-risk AI systems should be accompanied by relevant documentation and clear information, including potential risks to fundamental rights. Although these prior documents are not specific about what to communicate, they highlight the importance of sharing system details with potential users. This explains the relevance of the model cards.

The JRC study [6] adapts the seven key requirements for trustworthy AI systems outlined in the ALTAI to the context of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs). The main contribution of this study to our work is the definition of a set of criteria for the AVs that can be used to fulfil the ALTAI's key requirements.

With the general transparency guidelines and the list of criteria from the JRC to make CCAM systems more trustworthy, we have developed new sections and content to include in the model card to increase transparency and tailor it to CCAM applications. The changes include aspects of a system that should be followed to be trustworthy and compliant with the current legislation, including information about the authors and communication channels as well as instructions of usage for the different users. It also includes relevant descriptions taken from the CCAM context, such as ODD (Operational Domain

Design), SAE level of autonomy [7], and more specific items related to mobility context. Fairness aspects are also covered by adding specific references to a fair evaluation that includes intended users, children, and people with disabilities. Some reordering and renaming of the sections were performed as well. To see a complete list of changes with respect to the last model card version presented in D3.1, see Table 1. Here, content added or removed is indicated with a “+” or a “-” symbol, respectively.

Table 1: Overview of changes with respect to D3.1

Section	Sub-section	Checklist Item
Introduction	Author details	+ Participation of each of the authors in the creation
	Model info	+ Brief description of the model interaction with users + Layer of technology it belongs to according to the JRC classification []
	+ Contact details	+ Name and affiliations of the contact + Email address + Website or phone number
Model Details	MLOps architecture	+ Description of the system the model is integrated into (e.g., inference engine, data pre-processing or post-processing) + Describe the online continuous training process. + Description of the model updating process and criteria + A MLOps Card can be provided as a complement, which is highly advisable
	Training data	+ Purpose of the dataset (intended use) + Additional information on the validation split if different from the training split
	Evaluation data	+ Purpose of the dataset (intended use)
Intended Use and Recommendations	Use cases & Users	+ Layer of technology it belongs to according to the JRC classification (localization, scene understanding, path planning, control, user interaction) + Level(s) of vehicle automation of the SAE standard that is intended to be implemented + Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) of the system that is intended to be implemented + Risk classification according to the AI Act + Description of developers’ limitations (location, private sector, public, government, etc.) + Level of expertise or technical knowledge required to implement the model + Other uses of the model (possible uses of the model besides the one described in this model card) + Relevant information for people with disabilities + Relevant information for children + Role of the users in the mobility context (e.g., driver, passenger, VRU) + Specified human-related assumptions and fixed values when building the model (human height, weight, Fitzpatrick skin types, age) + Expertise required to interact with the model

	+ Usage and recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Brief description and details of where to find technical documentation + Instructions for developers to access the model for implementation + Guidance on how to use the model's output in downstream applications + Explanation of how to interact with the model + Description of all intended human interactions with the model + Strategies implemented for human oversight + Description of how to exercise oversight + Methods of communicating to the users that they are interacting with the system + Guidance on how to identify unexpected behaviours that need to be reported + Channel of communication to report incidences or incidents + Channel of communication to give feedback about user's interactions
	- Limitations	Removed sub-section and added its items into new section Limitations and Risks (see below)
Evaluation & Performance	Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Metrics of overall performance (mission accomplished, per km failure rate, per km accident rate, # of manual interventions) + Other AVs performance metrics like the ones suggested in JRC (please specify) + Real data / real scenarios evaluation procedures + ODD test coverage + External parties' certifications or audits + Stakeholder participation in the evaluation + Description of user tests and user studies
	Results	+ Performance on simulated data, test tracks and real traffic situations
	+ Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Explanation of the strategy of continuous monitoring + Measurement of concept drift + Measurement of data drift + Description of periodical tests and maintenance
- Usage & Risks	- Usage and recommendations - Risks	Section removed. Items moved to new sections Intended Use and Recommendations and Limitations and Risks
+ Limitations and Risks	+ Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Old items from the removed limitations sub-section + ODD-related limitations (e.g., the model only works with certain scenarios) + Reporting of any known failures of the system + Specification if it is sensible to occlusions + Specification if a calibration step is needed + Description of the fallback plan + Description of system behaviour when failure or outside the ODD

		+ Description of system behaviour when close to the limits of ODD
	+ Risks & Impact	+ Impact on end-users' life + Impact on society + Environmental impact + Description of compliance with the key requirements
Ethical Considerations	Fairness	+ Diversity of end-users included in the data + Diversity of users testing and validating the model + Description of inclusion in the analysis of people with disabilities + Description of inclusion in the analysis of children
	Privacy	+ Person blurring and license plate blurring + Link to consent and privacy agreements + Communication channel to the user to know their personal data treatment + Explanation of compliance with the GDPR
	+ Explainability	+ Description of explainable AI techniques to make the model's decisions more explainable (e.g., saliency maps) + Uncertainty measurement + Description of the logging system + Other used XAI techniques (please specify)
	- Accountability	Items added in the new sub-section Explainability

3 DATA AND INFORMATION FUSION TO REDUCE CONFLICTING PERCEPTION

3.1 Introduction

This chapter details the research conducted within Task 3.2, focusing on building trustworthy and interpretable perception systems for autonomous vehicles. Achieving these goals requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), model robustness, and sensor modality fusion.

There are two key aspects to building trust in autonomous vehicle perception systems: interpretability and robustness. Interpretability allows humans to understand how the system makes decisions, fostering trust and acceptance. Robustness ensures reliable object detection under diverse environmental conditions, further enhancing the system's credibility.

Task 3.2 explores various XAI techniques to make perception models more interpretable. This includes implementing transparent layers within the model architecture to reveal the rationale behind its decisions (Explainable Perception Modules) and visualizing uncertainties associated with the model's predictions (Model Uncertainty Quantification). By acknowledging areas where the system might be less confident, uncertainty visualization fosters trust.

This work package also investigates strategies to enhance multi-modal model robustness by establishing a new dataset and benchmark for state-of-the-art perception models.

The project leverages sensor fusion techniques to create a robust and reliable perception system. This involves integrating data from multiple sensors (e.g., camera and LiDAR) to compensate for individual sensor limitations and improve overall detection accuracy (Reliable Fusion of Sensor Modalities). Additionally, explainable methods for tracking multiple objects are implemented to enhance transparency the Multi-Object Tracking.

Figure 3: Conceptual overview of WP3.2 with the involved partners.

Task 3.2 research also contributes to improving Local Dynamic Maps (LDMs). These real-time databases fuse static and dynamic information from various sources, including the outputs of the perception

system. By providing a comprehensive and up-to-date picture of the environment, LDMs play a crucial role in explainable perception.

Ultimately, the research and developments within Task 3.2 contribute to the UC1 demonstrator by ensuring the trustworthiness, interpretability, and robustness of the perception system, paving the way for the safe and reliable operation of autonomous vehicles. A conceptual overview of this WP including the involved partners is shown in Figure 3.

3.2 Explainable perception modules

The goal is to make all perception modules which are developed in this working package explainable during inference. While some architectures offer inherent mechanisms that can be exploited for explanation, like self-attention layers in transformers, other architectures may not. BUW aims to develop and test model-agnostic explainability methods usable for all involved partners. The following necessary criteria have been identified in collaboration with the involved partners:

- Analysis of features in the input that the model focuses on for object classification;
- Identification of learned biases towards certain features;
- Explanations for specific misclassifications.

3.2.1 Methodology

BUW has identified Detector Randomized Input Sampling for Explanation [8] (D-RISE) as a suitable state-of-the-art baseline method. While D-RISE has been shown to provide robust explanations, it is limited to single image inputs and requires too many inferences to be real-time capable in its current form. BUW's first research contribution is extending D-RISE to accommodate multi-sensor inputs and enable offline detection. To this end, BUW has familiarized itself with the nuScenes dataset, as most of the latest state-of-the-art models benchmark their results on this dataset, and worked through the state-of-the-art of multi-image object detection models for autonomous driving. Preliminary results of extending the scope of D-RISE to multi-sensor inputs on the CAPE algorithm [9] show promising results to provide comprehensive explanations on multi-sensor fusion models that are in line with real-world scenarios and expert reasoning.

3.2.2 Results and next steps

Moving forward, we will delve further into the transfer of these insights to model-specific explainability with a focus on real-time explainability of the perception modules. This includes, but is not limited to, attention-based XAI methods, which IKA has already implemented in their model, and gradient-based methods. The quality and usefulness of explanations will be assessed in comparison to offline D-RISE explanations as the baseline. In the final step, an explainer model will be trained in a supervised manner to predict D-RISE explanations given an image and class. The hypothesis is that this method can combine the advantages of D-RISE and recent advances in generative models for real-time explanations.

3.3 Transformer-based Saliency Maps

3.3.1 Introduction

Vision Transformers (ViTs) have made significant strides in the field of computer vision, achieving state-of-the-art results on a wide range of scene understanding tasks for automated driving. The idea is that the transformers’ attention mechanism can capture a global understanding of the scene and therefore generates more accurate detections while eliminating the need for handcrafted postprocessing or object fusion steps. This end-to-end approach offers many advantages, but it also presents a challenge in terms of explainability. This challenge becomes particularly crucial when considering the deployment of ViTs in safety-critical applications like autonomous driving. In such scenarios, it is essential for authorities, developers, and users to have a clear understanding of the model’s reasoning behind its predictions.

3.3.2 Methodology

In this context, IKA proposed a saliency map generation approach for a multi-camera transformer model, aiming to enhance the understanding of the model’s behaviour and provide valuable insights into which regions of input images are most influential in determining object detection predictions [10]. Saliency maps are visualizations that highlight the regions in an image that an object detection model finds most influential for its prediction. Saliency maps can be considered as heatmaps that are overlaid on the original image, where brighter areas indicate elements the model considered most important for its decision.

The proposed method by IKA generates such saliency maps during runtime of the model which outperforms expensive gradient-based methods. The effectiveness of the approach was validated through comprehensive perturbation tests. See Figure 4 for an overview.

Figure 4 IKA investigated how saliency maps as visual explanations for a multi-camera transformer-based 3D object detector can be efficiently generated. IKA performed extensive perturbation tests to evaluate raw transformer attention and gradient-based methods.

In this approach, the model’s attention layers are used to produce saliency maps for the interactions in the cross- and self-attention. In the following, different gradient-free and gradient-based computation and propagation rules are presented.

Gradient-Based Methods

- Grad-CAM
- Gradient Rollout

Raw-Attention Methods

- Raw Attention Last Layer
- Raw Attention Mean-Layer Fusion
- Raw Attention Max-Layer Fusion

IKA performed extensive experiments on the nuScenes dataset. First, a qualitative visual exploration of the attentions maps to better understand the mechanism of the architecture was conducted, as shown in Figure 5. Second, a quantitative evaluation tested the quality produced by each method using positive and negative perturbation tests, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5 Saliency maps generated for different objects classes using all explainability methods.

Figure 6 Positive perturbation test evaluated on the nuScenes validation set. Smaller AUC is better.

The nuScenes dataset [16] was recorded with a multi-camera setup consisting of six cameras which have a partial overlap in their FOVs. The investigated transformer architecture projects each query onto all camera frames, enabling a global attention on all input images. This end-to-end approach generates a single detection for objects that appear in two or more cameras at the same time. In such cases, the attention is distributed on the overlapping parts of the object, as shown in Figure 7. The approach also allows to increase the traceability of the detector network by estimating the contribution of each camera to the current detection, as indicated by the green bars in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Raw cross-attention examples for objects (green OBB) that lie in the overlapping FOV of two cameras. In each example, a single query is used to generate the saliency maps for all camera images. Attention can be observed on the object on both overlapping images.

3.3.3 Results and next steps

The approach, based on raw cross-attention, proved to be more efficient than gradient-based methods. Perturbation test demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed approach. Visual exploration of attention maps showed that the transformer’s attention alternates between different concepts of a class in different layers to distinguish between classes and to determine object properties. Aggregating attention across different layers was crucial for a comprehensive explanation. The insights gained from this study pave the way to develop an explainable 3D object detector for WP3 and UC1.

3.4 Perception Model Robustness

Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) must comprehend their surrounding environment—vehicles, pedestrians, cyclists, and their respective postures—to further estimate the speed or future trajectories of these moving objects and plan their own motions accordingly. While advancements have been made in the domain of autonomous driving perception, most testing and training of perception models is conducted under optimal weather and road conditions with clear visibility. Urban noise, weather and traffic conditions significantly impact the safety and operability of AVs. For autonomous vehicles to gain widespread acceptance and trust, they must demonstrate robustness, reliability and accuracy under adverse weather and road conditions. Within WP3, model robustness for LiDAR-Camera fusion (see 3.4.1) and weight fusion on the robustness for the CLIP [11] model (see 3.4.4) have been explored.

3.4.1 Robustness LiDAR-Camera Fusion - Introduction

Regarding Multi-Modal sensor setups with multiple cameras and LiDARs, additional issues like miscalibration during the vehicle's motion, and sensor misalignments in terms of varying frequencies

or latencies often lead to deviations between sensor modalities. These problems are of particular interest when multi-modal detection methods are employed. Their effectiveness and robustness largely depend on how and where information is fused within the model.

Figure 8: MultiCorrupt consists of ten synthetic corruption types that affect LiDAR (L), multi-view cameras (C), or both modalities (LC).

3.4.2 Robustness LiDAR-Camera Fusion - Methodology

Building on these considerations, a consistent and open-source evaluation framework for assessing the robustness of multi-modal detection algorithms has been developed by IKA. The evaluation dataset and framework - named MultiCorrupt [12] - consist of 10 multi-modal sensor corruptions, as shown in Figure 8. MultiCorrupt is open sourced at <https://github.com/ika-rwth-aachen/MultiCorrupt>, allowing researchers to easily test and benchmark their own models. The benchmark includes the following corruptions:

- **Darkness:** Simulates low light conditions with Poisson Gaussian noise.
- **Brightness:** Introduces overexposure by adding brightness in the HSV space of the images.
- **Points Reducing:** Randomly drops points from the point cloud, with the fraction of removed points increasing with the severity level.
- **Temporal Misalignment:** Applies temporal misalignment to camera and point cloud data to simulate imperfect synchronization between different modalities.
- **Spatial Misalignment:** Introduces both translation and rotation misalignment between the point cloud and camera inputs, varying the angle of rotation and proportion of affected data depending on the severity level.
- **Motion Blur:** Incorporates jitter noise into the data to replicate motion, vibrations, and the rolling shutter effect.
- **Missing Camera:** Randomly drops frames from multiple cameras at each timestamp to simulate frame loss.
- **Beams Reducing:** Reduces the number of LiDAR beams with increasing severity levels.

- **Fog:** Simulates fog in point clouds using a method that translates the parameters of LiDAR fog generation into an image fog generation method.
- **Snow:** Uses an approach that samples snow particles and models them as opaque spheres, and models the reflection properties of wet ground surfaces. Corrupts point cloud and image data corresponding to defined levels of snowfall.

3.4.3 Robustness LiDAR-Camera Fusion - Results and next steps

We evaluate five state-of-the-art multi-modal detectors on MultiCorrupt and analyse their performance in terms of their resistance ability. Our results show that existing methods exhibit varying degrees of robustness depending on the type of corruption and their fusion strategy, as shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Robustness enhancing model design choices are “independent modality handling”, either through independent modality-spaces for Transformer tokens and queries or modality independent detection branches. Masked-modal training seems to boost robustness but requires further analysis to determine if it is applicable across a variety of architectures. Robustness diminishing factors are singular modality-dependant query initialization or a deep coupling of multi-modal features early in the detection pipeline. This benchmark not only sheds light on the current landscape of robustness in multi-modal 3D object detection but also helps us to create a robust and trustworthy 3D object detector for WP3 and UC1.

Model	Beams Red.	Brightness	Darkness	Fog	Missing Cam.	Motion Blur	Points Red.	Snow	Spatial Mis.	Temporal Mis.	mRA
CMT [1]	0.786	0.985	0.948	0.806	0.974	0.841	0.925	0.833	0.809	0.788	0.870
DeepInteraction [5]	0.655	0.984	0.929	0.583	0.842	0.832	0.882	0.759	0.731	0.768	0.796
TransFusion [4]	0.633	0.998	0.988	0.754	0.985	0.826	0.851	0.748	0.685	0.777	0.824
SparseFusion [2]	0.689	0.992	0.963	0.767	0.954	0.848	0.879	0.770	0.714	0.777	0.835
BEVfusion [3]	0.676	0.987	0.969	0.752	0.974	0.866	0.872	0.774	0.705	0.742	0.832

Figure 9: Robustness for all corruptions and severity levels. Robustness Ability for different severity levels computed using NDS score.

Figure 10 Relative robustness visualization. Relative Robustness computed with NDS using BEVfusion as baseline.

3.4.4 Weight Fusion - Introduction

This work explores the impact of weight fusion on the robustness of the CLIP model [11].

CLIP [1] has shown that it has an outstanding robustness capability in the zero-shot case, i.e., if no fine-tuning is performed. A fine-tuning of CLIP reduces the robustness ability significantly, which led to an investigation of the regeneration of its robustness ability by using weight fusion as a method.

3.4.5 Weight Fusion - Methodology

Based on the traffic sign classification, a variety of experiments were conducted to show the influence of weight fusion. To measure the prediction performance of CLIP, the top-1 and top-5 error rate were used as KPIs. To test the zero-shot performance, CLIP was initialized with the weights generated on 400 million image-text pairs during training. The three datasets GTSRB [13], Mapillary [14] and ZOD [15] were used to fine-tune CLIP. The resulting weights were averaged with the initial weights by weighted averaging in 0.1 steps, resulting in 9 averaged/fused weights.

3.4.6 Weight Fusion - Results and next steps

Figure 11 shows the results after fine-tuning on ZOD (in-distribution): Weight fusion was found to have a significant influence on the robustness capability. If only the in-distribution performance is considered, weight fusion can also lead to an improvement in all cases.

Figure 11: Left: Top-1 error rate; Right: Top-5 error rate

3.5 Perception Model Optimization

3.5.1 Introduction

One of the key challenges for autonomous mobility is the computing power of the server in the vehicle. There could be multiple AI models running on the server such as object detection, path planning, manoeuvring etc., and most of them require extensive computing power. Unfortunately, there are limitations on the computing resources available in the vehicle as it is infeasible to install a high-end server owing to space and cost constraints. One approach to solving this problem would be to transfer the raw data to a cloud server, run the AI models, and transfer the results back to the vehicle. However, to ensure this, the vehicle must always drive in a secure, high-speed, and reliable network.

3.5.2 Methodology

To overcome these challenges, BUW proposes model compression as an alternative approach. Traditionally, this has been achieved either using quantization (typically 16-bit) or through model-pruning. Our approach proposes a modification of the backbone network which results in model compression without significantly impacting the performance compared to the original model, as shown in Figure 12. Currently, we implement this approach only for the object detection task, but it can also be extended to tasks such as segmentation, tracking etc.

Figure 12: A typical architecture of LiDAR based Object Detectors

In the customization of the backbone network, we draw insights from existing models like PeleeNet and MobileNet, which propose state-of-the-art compression methodologies specifically designed for image data. Our approach combines the best of two models and extends the methodology for 3D point cloud-based object detection.

3.5.3 Results and next steps

Currently, we have implemented this approach for the model: Complex-YOLO on KITTI dataset. We are currently implementing the same on state-of-the-art models trained on the nuScenes dataset such as PointPillars.

3.6 Model Uncertainty

3.6.1 Introduction

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) is an essential aspect of perception systems, as it provides valuable information about the reliability and confidence of the detected objects. Understanding the uncertainty associated with object detection in LiDAR point clouds allows autonomous vehicles to make more informed decisions, especially in safety-critical scenarios.

In recent years, Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) has been used as a technique for uncertainty quantification in deep learning models. By leveraging dropout during both training and inference, MCD enables the estimation of epistemic uncertainty, which captures model uncertainty arising from limited training data. This uncertainty estimation technique has shown promising results in various computer vision tasks, including image classification, segmentation, and depth estimation. However, it is computationally expensive and therefore not suitable for real-time applications.

A technique called Last Layer Monte Carlo Dropout (LLMCD) is proposed by IKA to address this issue. LLMCD basically applies MCD only to the detection head of the model, while the encoder part stays untouched. The goal of IKA's work is to investigate LLMCD as a Monte Carlo Dropout based Uncertainty Quantification for 3D object detection in LiDAR point clouds by extending existing state-of-the-art object detection frameworks and integrating dropout-based uncertainty estimation.

3.6.2 Methodology

Introducing the LLMCD method results in pivotal modifications to the original PBOD model [16]. Last Layer refers to the regression head phase that is modified. Each pillar of the detection head uses only one head for the occupancy probability and the classification vector. However, for the regression vector, multiple heads are used. Each of these heads operates on the same abstract tensor derived from the same feature extractor. However, they ideally focus on varying characteristics within the tensor, leading to the prediction of distinct bounding boxes. By diversifying the attention of the regression head, the system aims to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of potential object locations within the point cloud.

The second significant alteration is the incorporation of dropout not just during the training phase, as traditionally observed, but also during inference. The consistent application of dropout during inference aids in producing varied outputs for the same input. As a result, it becomes feasible to capture a range of potential bounding box predictions for a given point cloud, thereby providing a quantifiable measure of the model's uncertainty.

Figure 13: Deep sub-ensembles with Monte Carlo layers for Pillar-OD

One inherent challenge in evaluating a model’s UQ capability is the absence of a ground truth for uncertainty. Unlike traditional object detection where the correctness of a bounding box prediction can be directly compared with a known ground truth, uncertainty does not have a concrete reference point. This challenge is addressed by the NLL (Negative Log Likelihood) score. Qualitatively speaking, the NLL score is a measure of how well the uncertainty of the model aligns with the actual uncertainty. A low NLL score indicates that the model’s uncertainty is close to the actual uncertainty and thus the UQ is good. Low NLL scores occur when the model is very certain about its prediction, and the ground truth is close to the prediction. Even with a prediction that deviates significantly from the ground truth, the model can still achieve a low NLL score if it is uncertain about its output.

3.6.3 Results and Next Steps

For the evaluation of the proposed approach, the nuScenes dataset is used for training and testing. In each experiment, the same training and test set is used to ensure that the results are comparable. For all training runs with LLMCD, $n = 20$ detection heads with a dropout rate of $p = 0.2$ are used.

Model	AP cars@0.5	Model	NLL cars@0.5
Vanilla PBOD	0.6559	Vanilla PBOD	n.a.
PBOD + LLMCD	0.5389	PBOD + LLMCD	-3.17
PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.5$	0.5046	PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.5$	-3.51
PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.75$	0.2966	PBOD + LLMCD + SML $\beta = 0.75$	-3.42
Ensemble n=5	0.6078	Ensemble n=5	18.7
Ensemble n=10	0.607	Ensemble n=10	-3.18

Figure 14: Detection accuracy and NLL uncertainty score for the different model variants.

The vanilla PBOD model [16] achieved the best detection performance. While the LLMCD method offered real-time capability with good overall performance and UQ estimates, it came at a cost. Increasing the beta hyperparameter in LLMCD worsened detection performance, suggesting a trade-off between uncertainty quantification accuracy and detection. Further exploration of this trade-off and optimization strategies is recommended (refer to D5.2 for more details of the evaluation).

3.7 LiDAR-Radar-Camera Fusion

3.7.1 Introduction

Fusing perception information from LiDAR, Radar, and camera data is proposed, as all these sensors have distinct advantages relative to each other. While cameras are offering rich visual information for detecting objects and patterns, they are heavily affected from lightning conditions (e.g. during night-time the scene objects are not visible). Radars, from the other hand, perform better in different weather and light conditions, however they lack spatial resolution compared to the LiDARs and cameras. In addition, while LiDAR offer high depth precision and are independent from lightning conditions, they are affected by the weather conditions, such as snow or fog. Leveraging all the unique strengths from each sensor is essential for generating an accurate representation of the surrounding environment compared to single sensor approaches. To achieve this, a 3D LiDAR-based object detection pipeline is applied to the LiDAR data, which is then combined with the Radar object list to extract the relative distance, velocity, and accelerations of actors in the scene (the same principle can also be applied with 2D camera-based object detection). The outcome is a “perception” time series database which can be used for driving scenario detection and safety analysis assessment.

3.7.2 Methodology

Due to the limited amount of person months (1PM) SIE-BE has in this task, the proposed methodology was to merge object level data from LiDAR and Radar data (see Figure 12) as well as performing camera-Radar and camera-LiDAR fusion (Figure 13) in the SIE-BE dataset, which was generated in D2.1 [17]. To apply sensor fusion strategies in this dataset, it is important to calibrate all perception sensors intrinsically and extrinsically. For this reason, an offline target-based calibration method was used to achieve highly accurate results. For the perception sensors, an optimization-based algorithm was utilized to perform extrinsic and intrinsic calibration.

Next, a 3D LiDAR-based object detection and tracking model was utilized to detect 3D objects in the scene, while for the Radar sensors the resulting 3D object list was used, which was generated by providing vehicle motion information to the ARS548 sensors during the recording campaign. Then, the radar object list was merged in the LiDAR coordinate frame and based on proximity metrics, it was paired with the generated 3D LiDAR-based bounding boxes. By pairing these two lists, a perception-time series database can be generated, which includes the relative distance, the velocity, and acceleration of the surrounding objects in the recording.

Figure 15: Sensor Fusion in the LiDAR coordinate frame of the Continental ARS548 sensor data and merging the object lists of the two sensors on the SIE-BE generated dataset.

Figure 16: Sensor Fusion on the SIE-BE generated dataset. Left: Camera-LiDAR Fusion, Right: Camera-Radar Fusion

3.7.3 Results and next steps

Figure 17 gives an overview of the time series representation of the extracted LiDAR-Radar fused object lists (object distance, object absolute velocity, object relative velocity, object absolute acceleration, TTC, THW) for a specific actor in the scene. Additionally, SIE-BE is interested in exploring the possibility of performing track-to-track fusion in the future by combining 3D camera-based models in addition to the radar and LiDAR perception and increase the robustness of the 3D object detection and tracking.

Figure 17: Time series representation of the extracted LiDAR-Radar fused object lists for a specific actor in the scene.

3.8 LiDAR-Camera Fusion

3.8.1 Introduction

Developed by CAF, the LiDAR-Camera fusion algorithm offers a complementary approach to environmental perception for autonomous vehicles, leveraging the unique strengths of each technology. LiDAR excels in producing accurate 3D representations of surroundings, providing precise distance measurements unaffected by lighting variations, which is crucial for the spatial localization of objects. Conversely, cameras deliver high-resolution colour imagery, essential for identifying objects based on appearance and texture. Therefore, this fusion algorithm combines the depth perception offered by LiDAR with the detailed visual insights provided by cameras offering a richer and a more detailed understanding of the vehicle's environment.

3.8.2 Methodology

By integrating these technologies, the algorithm can create a robust and comprehensive object list to accurately reflect the real-world environment around the autonomous vehicle. This list is vital for making informed decisions about vehicle manoeuvres, especially in complex driving scenarios that involve lane changes and navigation among other road users.

The structure of the algorithm consists of the following steps (see Figure 18 for a diagram overview):

- **LiDAR 3D Detections:** This block represents the detections made by the LiDAR sensor, which provides three-dimensional information about the objects around the vehicle. These 3D detections are crucial as they provide accurate distance and shape information, which is vital for understanding the vehicle's environment.
- **Change Referential:** After obtaining 3D detections, the data undergoes a referential change. This step is about transforming the 3D detection data into a coordinate system that is compatible with the camera's 2D detections. This process is essential for aligning the information gathered from the different sensors, enabling effective fusion of the data.
- **Camera 2D Detections:** In parallel to the 3D detections, the camera provides 2D detections. The camera captures visual information from the vehicle's surroundings, identifying objects based on their appearance in two dimensions (height and width).
- **Reprojection:** The reprojection step involves mapping the 3D detections onto the camera's 2D image plane. This is crucial for correlating the LiDAR and camera data, as it helps to verify if the objects detected by LiDAR in three dimensions correspond to those detected by the camera in two dimensions.
- **IoU (Intersection over Union):** IoU is the metric used to evaluate how much the 3D detections overlap with the reprojected 2D detections on the camera's image plane. A higher IoU score indicates a better match between the detections from the two sensors, which is a crucial factor in the fusion process.
- **Decision:** Based on the IoU scores, a decision-making process determines which detections from both sensors should be considered as accurate representations of the same objects. This

step is where the algorithm decides on the final list of detected objects by considering both the LiDAR and camera data.

- **Final Structure:** The outcome of the decision block is the final structure of the detected environment. This final structure is a unified representation of the vehicle's surroundings, combining both 3D and 2D detections into a single, coherent model. This information can then be used for the model environment when developing the lane change detection algorithm.

Figure 18: The fusion algorithm general architecture

3.8.3 Results and next steps

The result of this algorithm will be explained in more detail in Section 4 concerning CAF activities in the context of UC2-2.

3.9 Explainable Object Level Fusion

3.9.1 Introduction

Autonomous mobility relies on accurate perception for safe navigation, but individual sensor modalities often fall short. Sensor fusion addresses this by integrating data from multiple sensors, reducing limitations, and improving accuracy.

A robust Multimodal and Multi-Object Tracking (MOT) [18] method developed by IDIADA is applied on top of unimodal detections generated with AI models to increase perceptual robustness and manage conflicting perceptions. AI-based model outcomes are difficult to interpret and explain, while the MOT by design allows to make the data fusion more explainable and traceable:

- Explainability by visualizing detections and knowing which sensor relates to each detection.
- Explainability by collecting data fusion statistics (perceptions conflicts and differences).

3.9.2 Methodology

IDIADA's method is based on an advanced approach for Multi-Object Tracking (MOT) leveraging unsynchronized multimodal detections sourced from a diverse array of sensors, including cameras, radars, and LiDARs. This method entails the integration of modality-specific detectors to process

information from each sensor. Subsequently, these detections are fused within the MOT module, which encompasses a sophisticated combination of Kalman filtering and tracklet management algorithms.

To ensure the practical applicability of this method in real-world driving scenarios, it addresses challenges such as localization errors, misclassifications, and incomplete bounding-box detections originating from the object detector. This involves implementing robust strategies within the MOT module to effectively handle these issues and maintain accurate tracking performance amidst real-world complexities. An overview of the detection and tracking pipeline is displayed in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Multi-object tracking from sensor fusion. The proposed system receives inputs from a configurable set of sensors (camera, radar, and LiDAR, in our configuration). Modality-specific object detectors generate 3D detections that are then combined by means of a Kalman Filter to obtain more robust and stable 3D tracks. The corresponding equations and terminology used can be found in [15].

3.9.3 Results and next steps

The first demo of the MOT method has been applied to a ROS2 bag file with LiDAR object detections generated by IKA's AI model using the ROS2 framework. The visualization of the outcomes is depicted in Figure 20, with detected objects marked by blue bounding boxes and their corresponding tracks denoted by green bounding boxes. However, due to the lack of multimodal sensor data and noisy LiDAR detections with quite a few false positives, definitive conclusions from the MOT analysis are limited at this stage. Nonetheless, the preliminary results are promising.

Next steps will focus on refining the MOT algorithm by leveraging less noisy detections and integrating multimodal sensor data to perform sensor fusion. This fusion aims to enhance the reliability and interpretability of data fusion processes, thereby facilitating traceability and explainability in the overall system.

Figure 20: MOT applied to LiDAR object detections using ROS2.

3.10 Local Dynamic Maps

3.10.1 Introduction

A Local Dynamic Map (LDM) implementation aims to provide a centralised database inside an AV to store information in real-time from different data sources (see Figure 21). These sources are usually categorized into different layers, including a static layer (i.e., map information), a dynamic layer (i.e., 3D Object detections, V2X messaging, etc.) and intermediary layers of quasi-static (i.e., traffic signs) and transient data (i.e., traffic light signal phase) if the information is available. This database can be queried by different modules inside a vehicle to obtain the latest available information received or generated by the CCAV.

Figure 21 Generic overview of the functional architecture of the LDM component.

3.10.2 Methodology

An initial version of an LDM implementation has been developed in ROS2 to allow data insertion from the ROS2 topics of the test vehicles into the database. A Python API has been developed to serve as a connector between the ROS2 topics and the LDM. InfluxDB, a Time Series Database (TSDB), has been selected to store the relevant information in real time from the ROS2 topics. The TSDB is connected to Grafana, an interactive visualization web application that allows to create dashboards for data visualization and analysis. As a proof of concept to test the solution, a data parser from the NuScenes dataset [19] to the LDM has been developed and tested.

3.10.3 Results and next steps

The LDM currently only supports dynamic data (i.e., pedestrians, vehicles, etc.). A Grafana dashboard to visualize the data has been configured, as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Visualization using Grafana of a scene extracted from the NuScenes dataset. The data is queried in real-time from the information stored in the TSDB of the LDM.

Next steps will include adding static data (map information) from open-source solutions such as OpenStreetMap and adapting the current parser to work with recordings captured from the test vehicles including the perception of the modules developed by other partners in T3.2.

4 TRANSPARENT EDGE-CASE TRAINING USING MIXED REAL-SYNTHETIC DATA AND SAFETY-CRITICAL AND TRUSTWORTHY PREDICTIVE MODELS

4.1 Introduction

T3.3 Transparent edge-case training using mixed real-synthetic data and T3.4 Safety-critical and trustworthy predictive models are heavily intertwined, as also shown in Section 1.3. Therefore, in this chapter the work on the development of AI algorithms that are related to those topics is combined. Figure 23 provides the approach and dependencies between the different modules that have been developed so far. Specifically, for use case 2.2 (further noted as UC2.2), work was allocated to develop dedicated algorithms to demonstrate UC2.2 at a later stage in the project. The work done by the partners involved in that use case is therefore explicitly mentioned in this chapter.

Figure 23: Approach and dependencies between T3.3, T3.4, and specifically UC2.2

The objectives of the algorithms developed in this chapter are to

1. improve data efficiency and robustness of the predictive models using mixed real-synthetic data to train deep neural networks for edge cases
2. increase the explainability and trustworthiness of the predictive models using hybrid AI techniques that provide the closest physical explanation to the prediction of a deep data-driven approach

4.2 Collision risk prediction

4.2.1 Introduction

Road accidents are still a major concern of both the automotive industry and society, as 1.35 million people worldwide lose their lives in traffic every year [20]. The current industry standards in collision risk prediction are limited by their limited ability in predicting possible collisions under dynamic and complex movement patterns that are frequent on rural and urban roads.

In this task, we develop a deep data-driven, image-based collision risk prediction model that uses mixed data and is designed to handle edge-case urban scenarios.

4.2.2 Methodology

We adopted an image-based collision risk prediction model developed by TU/e called 'RiskNet' [21]. The initial version of the model is reproduced and extended. The risk of collision is predicted using the RiskNet deep neural network architecture, which produces only binary results (whereby 0 is safe and 1 is unsafe). The model adopts a decoupling learning strategy, which means that training is done using only simulated video data, while real-life data is used for testing (see Figure 26). To overcome the big structural difference between real-life data and synthetic data, the model uses attention mask and optical flow as a domain resilient intermediate representation. For this model a Prescan dataset and YouTube videos, namely the YDID dataset, are used for simulated and real-life data respectively. Additionally, we have validated the trained (only using simulated data) model with IDIADA test-track data.

Figure 24: Decoupled learning strategy

4.2.3 Results and next steps

The model successfully generalizes to the real-life data and shows promising results. We compared the result of the RiskNet with manually annotated video of a scenario on an intersection with a car coming from the right junction, almost hitting the bike the bike coming from the left. The blue bar below in Figure 25 indicates the risk moment that is manually annotated (ground truth) while the above yellow bar indicates the result (risk moment) as predicted by our RiskNet model. It shows that the model accurately predicts a risk.

Figure 25: Collision risk prediction validated on IDIADA dataset (car to bike turning scenario)

For next steps, we will validate our model on more IDIADA datasets. We will also use and apply Grad-CAM techniques [22] to the RiskNet module to visually explain which actor in the scene/scenario has activated and triggered the risk situation.

Additionally, a model-based approach for collision risk prediction, developed by IDIADA based on an improved method to calculate the Time-to-Collision (TTC) of two vehicles [23], will be integrated with the TU/e AI model to make the prediction of the data-driven approach trustworthy by providing the closest physical explanation to the prediction of the AI model.

4.3 Domain adaptation strategy for training with real and synthetic data

4.3.1 Introduction

Machine learning systems encounter limitations stemming from enough and relevant training data availability. This challenge is particularly pronounced in edge cases. Synthetic data can help alleviate these data needs if the domain gap between real and synthetic data is correctly handled or mitigated.

4.3.2 Methodology

VIC explores the best strategy to train a Deep Neural Network (DNN) using annotated synthetic data (source domain) and some unannotated real data (target domain) in the following classification task.

Adverse weather conditions usually have a minority representation in training data for AI models but are critical to analyse how a system behaves in different conditions (e.g., ODD). The synthetic dataset SHIFT [24] contains extensive labelled examples for different weather conditions. We explore different strategies to train a DNN to classify the weather of a scene captured by an RGB camera. We use the following automotive datasets: the SHIFT dataset as the synthetic source domain and the BBDK100 dataset [25] as the target real domain.

The following Figure 26 shows an example of a synthetic image (foggy class) and a real image (clear class).

Figure 26: Example of a synthetic image (foggy class) and a real image (clear class)

We only use the labels of BBDK100 for testing, but not for training, as our goal is to maximize the knowledge learnt using only synthetic data. We conduct the following experiments with different real-synthetic training strategies to train a classification DNN. The input RGB image is classified into 4 possible categories: clear, cloudy, foggy, or rainy.

Exp1 - Train a ResNet-101 DNN with annotated synthetic data and test with real data. Here we train a classification network from ImageNet pretrained weights with synthetic data. No domain adaptation strategy is used. All the images from the BBDK100 dataset are used for testing.

Exp2 - Train a ResNet-101 DNN with annotated synthetic data and unlabelled real data. Here we use the Unsupervised Domain Adaptation (UDA) training strategy presented in MIC [26], adapted to our problem. This approach combines the source training data with unlabelled target data with a new mask-based module to learn spatial context relations as additional clues in the training. We test the model with the real data from the BBDK100 dataset.

Exp3 - Train a ResNet-101 DNN with refined annotated synthetic data and unlabelled real data. To reduce the domain gap between the data distributions of synthetic and real images, we first apply FDM (Feature Distribution Matching) to synthetic images. Then, we use the same UDA training strategy (MIC) as in Exp2. The FDM algorithm [27] tries to match image statistics from source and target domains.

4.3.3 Results and next steps

The following table summarizes the accuracy we obtain for the different classes and experiments as well as the average for all the experiments.

Table 2: Accuracy for different classes of weather conditions

Experiment	Clear	Cloudy	Foggy	Rainy	Average
Exp1	94.0%	19.0%	0.0%	3.0%	29.0%
Exp2	81.0%	74.6%	76.2%	87.3%	79.8%
Exp3	85.7%	69.8%	60.3%	73.0%	72.2%

The results show that training with a domain adaptation strategy helps to improve the biased results obtained in the evaluation of Experiment 1, where almost all the real test images are classified as clear. Comparing Experiment 2 and 3, we conclude that trying to get data distributions closer with FDM before training with MIC strategy did not help, as results are similar and even a little bit lower (79.8% versus 72.2%). The best classified images in both experiments are those with clear and rainy conditions.

4.4 AI algorithm for application in UC2.2

The primary objective of UC2.2 is to enhance the robo-taxi's ability to navigate safely through urban traffic by predicting the intended motion of the traffic participants. This goal is achieved through the development of a comprehensive prediction module, which goes beyond a standalone prediction model. The module will incorporate components (see Figure 27) for (1) creating a representative urban scenario dataset, (2) processing raw sensor measurements to detect not only the traffic participants but additional scenario information, (3) generating motion predictions for detected traffic participants, and (4) implementing fault-tolerant decision-making. In the first development cycle, tasks will be completed independently to optimize the performance within each component's specific scope. Therefore, the following sections will provide a detailed overview of each component implemented by the partners collaborating on the overall objective of UC2.

Figure 27: Use case 2.2 architecture

4.4.1 Situational awareness feature enhanced object detection

Introduction

IFAG developed algorithms for object detection with situational awareness features, which are used for robust scene understanding/prediction based on camera data. These algorithms are embedded in the robust prediction modules for robo-taxis in urban environments within UC2 (AI extended Situational Awareness / Understanding).

Methodology

The following Situational Awareness features have been addressed in detail:

- traffic light colour detection (red, orange, green)
- detection of vehicle signal lights (brake lights, left/right indicators), and
- bounding box orientation of detected objects.

For all three target features, algorithms were designed and developed using deep learning approaches based on the well-established one-step detection strategy "You Only Look Once" (YOLO). The algorithms were initially trained on several public datasets, such as LISA, CARLA, Kitty, Cityscapes and Eurocity.

Results and next steps

The first promising results were obtained by evaluating the given KPIs, namely F1 score, Intersection over Union (IoU) and mean Average Precision (mAP). Traffic light colour detection is already showing very accurate and robust results. The detection of vehicle signal lights faces problems caused by the lack of high-quality training data sets. To overcome this problem, elements (referred to images and video streams) of different training data sets (as outlined above in the methodology paragraph) have been merged to create an adequate amount of training data, which will be continuously improved. For object orientation identification, the best results were obtained for pedestrians and cars, while the misclassification between cyclists and pedestrians in a frame with few pixels is an issue to be further addressed during the project. Based on the first conclusions, priorities for further improvement of the algorithms have been identified and will be addressed in the second iteration of the project. Full details are described in Deliverable D5.2 [1]

4.4.2 Free space and lane detection

Introduction

Beside the sensor fusion algorithm mentioned above, CAF has also developed a suite of algorithms aimed at enhancing autonomous vehicle navigation and safety. These algorithms encompass a free space detector and a lane detection algorithm. This multi-faceted approach integrates LiDAR and camera data, combining the strengths of each sensing modality to provide a robust solution for autonomous mobility.

Methodology

As mentioned above, CAF has developed two distinct algorithms: one for mapping navigable spaces using LiDAR data without deep learning techniques and another for detecting lane markings using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The first focuses on efficient space identification by adapting to environmental specifics and converting data for easy partitioning and obstacle detection. The second processes road images to accurately define lane boundaries, essential for navigation and driver assistance. For further insights, it's important to note that the latter algorithm was trained on a non-public CAF dataset, comprised of images from six cameras with 85,496 images in the training set and 19,428 in the test set. Both systems are designed for real-time application and seamless integration into various systems via a ROS2 interface. For a more detailed explanation of the methodologies, please refer to document D5.2 [1].

It is important to note that this algorithm was trained using a CAF dataset. The latter is not public but is composed of images collected from six cameras, with a training set containing 85,496 images and a test set containing 19,428 images.

Results and next steps

Initial tests have shown our free space detector to be efficient and effective, achieving 14.5 FPS on a Siemens dataset, with further evaluations planned on CAF's high-performance computers and tests with real data. Similarly, our lane detection algorithm has proven robust across various conditions, accurately identifying lane markings. This latter, in a second phase, will be tested as well in real-world scenarios to evaluate its efficiency.

More detailed results, interpretations, and figures are available in deliverable D5.2 [1].

In future a lane change detector (see Figure 27) will also be developed, which will therefore not be described here.

4.4.3 Object Detection

Introduction

An object detector has been developed as well by CAF in the context of UC2-2.

Methodology

Initially, the CAF employed YOLOv5, but later transitioned to using YOLO-NAS to tap into state-of-the-art improvements in neural architecture search that promise better accuracy and efficiency. This system was trained on a combination of a subset from the COCO2017 dataset and CAF's own data, encompassing 40,000 frames across 300 training epochs. It can identify up to 80 different object classes, aligning with the classifications found in the COCO dataset. Additionally, the system features a ROS2 interface.

Results and next steps

Our object detection evaluation method focuses on key performance indicators such as mAP, IoU, precision, recall, and F1 score, adhering to requirements specified in D5.1. This approach has proven effective in accurately detecting and localizing a wide range of objects in urban traffic environments, achieving notable metrics like mAP of 0.79, IoU of 0.80, and an F1 score of 0.80. Further details are described in D5.2 [1] as well as an example of the results. Further steps include testing the model with real-world scenarios.

4.4.4 Sensor fusion on object level

Introduction

In the context of its participation in UC2-2, CAF has developed a sensor fusion on the object level algorithm.

Methodology

The sensor fusion algorithm combines LiDAR and camera data using geometric principles instead of deep learning, enhancing object detection and spatial awareness in complex settings. It starts by projecting 3D LiDAR points onto a 2D camera image, aligning sensor data for accurate object localization within the camera's field of view. The algorithm calculates the intersection-over-union (IoU) between LiDAR projections and camera-detected objects, filtering out discrepancies to focus on mutually

confirmed objects. By transforming world coordinates into camera coordinates considering the camera's extrinsic parameters, it maintains accurate spatial relationships across different coordinate systems. This geometric approach ensures precision and reliability in data fusion. The fusion algorithm operates through a ROS2 interface.

Results and next steps

The fusion algorithm showed promising initial results. By providing a more detailed understanding of the environment through sensor data integration, this algorithm enhances the vehicle's ability to detect and interact with its surroundings accurately. An example of the algorithm's output is shown in Figure 2828 below.

Figure 2828: An example of the result of the fusion algorithm on a CARLA scenario

Figure 28 illustrates a visualization where our algorithm, in camera coordinates, detects objects (a car in green and a light in red) and compares these to 3D detections, with a processing time of 0.000018 seconds; for more details, see deliverable D5.2 [28].

The next steps for our data fusion algorithm involve testing it with real data. This phase is crucial to assess the effectiveness and reliability of our method under practical conditions.

4.4.5 Prediction and intended motion

Introduction

As part of the UC2.2 activities, Virtual Vehicle is tasked with the design and development of a motion prediction model to be used as part of the robo-taxi's navigation system. The model's scope is constrained by the scenarios often occurring in an urban environment, focusing specifically on those taking place at intersections.

Methodology

The proposed design of the prediction model is based on the integration of explainable approaches [29], [30], [31] in previously black-box DL models. We chose inherently explainable approaches. This shift allowed us to focus on creating a foundation for generating explanations rather than just producing explanations themselves. Their inherent explainability made it possible to introduce and leverage the prior scenario knowledge. The proposed design of the model not only increases the accuracy and robustness of the predictions but also their generalizability given the diversity of scenarios that occur in an urban environment.

Model development has been divided into stages with each stage introducing new types of interactions that can form between different scenario elements. Alternatively, each stage will expand the description of the considered scenarios, recognizing new scenario elements to form even more comprehensive situational awareness and generate more reliable predictions. Dividing the model development based on the included scenario elements allowed for a better understanding of the influence each element has on the prediction metrics. Additionally, it yielded a more efficient and systematic identification of special cases.

At the current stage, the model (Figure 29) is being trained to learn the influence of road infrastructure on the motion of traffic participants, specifically pedestrians. To support the current training of the model, special attention was given to the dataset preparation both of real-world (inD dataset [32]) and synthetic (CommonRoad [33]) scenarios. The preparation process consisted of generating bird's eye view (BEV) rasters containing map information and past trajectory recordings of the observed traffic participants. We assume that map information is available, which requires all raster images to include details of lanes, sidewalks, and crossings. The available scenario information is stored in a graph database that creates a local dynamic map (LDM) with added tools for updating and retrieving the relevant data. As such, the LDM allows not only the storing of the scenario data necessary for the motion prediction but also the additional enrichment of the data that is then translated onto a raster input.

Figure 29 Motion prediction module pipeline

Results and next steps

In the following stage, model training will be conducted on the dataset containing not only the infrastructure information but also the information on the states of the remaining traffic participants. Enriching the rasters with trajectory information of the surrounding traffic, participants will allow tracking of the performance metrics changes. It is expected that an analysis of the influence

interactions between different classes of traffic participants will be necessary, especially the influence relative to pedestrians' motion.

4.4.6 Virtual world - simulation

Introduction

Synthetic data (see Figure 30) is information that's artificially generated rather than produced by real-world events. Typically created using algorithms, synthetic data can be deployed to validate mathematical models and to train machine learning models. Data generated by a computer simulation can be seen as synthetic data. This encompasses most applications of physical modelling, such as music synthesizers or flight simulators. The output of such systems approximates the real thing but is fully algorithmically generated. Synthetic data is generated to meet specific needs or certain conditions that may not be found in the original, real data. Synthetic data are often generated to represent the authentic data and allows a baseline to be set. Another benefit of synthetic data is to protect the privacy and confidentiality of authentic data.

Methodology

Within the Althena project, first a digital twin is built using Simcenter Prescan, considering physics-based sensor models, Simcenter Amesim, considering a vehicle dynamics model and SUMO as traffic simulator.

Simcenter Prescan allows the definition and parametrization of the scenario in a flexible way. For vehicles, different models and colours can be selected, while for humans: gender, race, age can be chosen. Furthermore, environmental and illumination conditions specific for the operational design domain can be easily specified. There are three essential components to provide a good physics-based simulation: sensor specific information, simulation engine and digital twin of the world/environment.

Siemens NL extended the synthetic data set with LiDAR sensor data and defined an extended KITTI data format. Vicomtech has built a parser to transform the data from the extended KITTI data format to the ASAM OpenLABEL standard format [34]. Furthermore, the synthetic data set is planned to be extended with physics-based radar sensor output in the future.

Results and next steps

The synthetic data set is currently used by several consortium partners for training neural networks, testing algorithms and data pipelines used during neural networks training and object tracking.

As a future activity, we plan to generate variations of a simple dataset, considering changes in illumination and weather conditions. We will save this dataset in the OpenLABEL format and release it to the public domain. The visualization/replay of the data set in OpenLABEL format is going to be supported by the WebLABEL software tool from Vicomtech, which is in the public domain. Finally, Siemens NL is working on multiple targets tracking in combination with fault-detection and sensor fusion, using the synthetic data set.

Figure 30: Synthetic data: camera image and LiDAR point cloud

4.4.1 Safety-critical embedded execution concept

Introduction

TTTech Auto (TTTA) is focusing in T3.4 on developing a fault-tolerant decision-making subsystem concept as a basis for safe Automated Driving Systems. Designing the proposed architectural system concept enables SAE [7] Level 3 and 4 Automated Driving (AD) Systems for highly automated driving. It is essential to develop *safe* automated systems to prevent driving accidents. A specific focus of this module is functional safety and fail-operational performance (e.g., having all the necessary input protections needed for the automotive environment, capable of receiving trajectory data via redundant CAN buses, etc.).

In the following years, tens of millions of vehicles are expected to be equipped with L4 driving systems allowing safe and reliable sensor data processing for e.g. Highway Pilot functions, Valet Parking and Autonomous truck driving in case individual functions fail. The proposed subsystem fail-operational concept ensures functional safety by design and introduces the necessary level of redundancy and diversity in a system to prevent common cause failures that are hard to predict.

Figure 31: Move from SAE Level 2 to Level 4 system: from fail-silent to fail-operational (TTTA)

Methodology

In this project period, we have examined the requirements and constraints that the architecture for SAE Level 4 must fulfil in real-world scenarios. It is essential that critical events, whether external or internal, as well as hardware failures, do not result in an accident. Accordingly, we have developed a concept for a fault-tolerant decision-making subsystem, detailed below in *Results*. This concept addresses the UC2.2 safety requirements and, in general, takes the high safety and reliability requirements of global car manufacturers' mass-production programs into account and has broader applicability guaranteeing fail-operational performance of the AD systems which support the driver of a vehicle in routine situations and help to reduce the number of traffic accidents. We consider functional and non-functional requirements as well as performance characteristics and quality objectives to develop this architectural concept, which will be finalized in the second reporting period of the project.

Figure 32: SAE Level 4 system (fail-operational) mechanism (TTTA)

Results and next steps

Figure 31 shows the differences between Level 2 and Level 4 automated driving systems. The latter supposes that the safe operation of a vehicle is a responsibility of a system and is not only a subject to a human control at a steering wheel. Today, advanced sensors and computer technologies support the driver of a vehicle in most practical situations and allow to reduce the number of traffic accidents. However, it is difficult to precisely specify all edge cases that can be encountered in driving conditions. Therefore, TTech Auto is further developing a fail-operational system mechanism that achieves a systematic partitioning into independent Fault Containment Units to manage the complexity of the L4 system. The concept introduces a Safety Decision Logic approach based on Safety Monitor and Fallback AD mechanisms, as shown in Figure 32. This decision-making subsystem concept can be used as a separate Electronic Control Unit, or ECU, which is ASIL D compliant to be used as a voter in automated driving systems.

5 EXPLAINABLE AND ROBUST DECISION MAKING (MANOEUVRE AND TRAJECTORY)

5.1 Introduction

T3.5 Explainable and robust decision making is related to the superior processing step, namely the planning of reasonable driving behaviours of an automated driving software pipeline. Therefore, this chapter outlines the work on the development of AI algorithms that are related to this topic. Figure 33 provides the approaches and dependencies between the different modules that are developed in T3.5.

The implemented algorithms are based on several inputs like object lists derived from modules related to the task of perception (T3.2) and their respective predictions (T3.4). Moreover, these algorithms utilize additional sources of information like digital maps or information derived from Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication. The implemented algorithms will be integrated into various demonstrators as part of UC3.

The algorithms developed in T3.5 can be divided into the three subtasks of recreating critical driving scenarios, the implementation of a hybrid AI motion planning system, and the modelling of context-dependant competence. The subtasks are described in more detail in the following chapters.

Figure 33: Approach and dependencies within T3.5

The overall objective of T3.5 is to improve robustness and understandability for decision-making modules by:

- combining data-driven- and knowledge-based AI for decision-making,
- modelling the competence of data-driven AI systems for decision-making to properly react to unforeseen situations,

- deriving challenging scenarios for the targeted training of data-driven AI systems for decision making, and
- explaining decisions to human occupants through visualization of decisions.

5.2 Hybrid AI motion planning

5.2.1 Introduction

The task of planning reasonable decisions and deriving the actual vehicle movement in the form of trajectories represents the final, overarching task within the pipeline of automated driving systems. This is followed by calculating the control variables for the actuators based on the generated trajectories, which then lead to the final realisation of the planned movement.

In this final processing step, all previously generated information, e.g. from the perception and prediction modules, is used and combined with other information sources such as digital maps or V2X information.

For this reason, the accuracy and robustness of all previously generated information influences the accuracy and robustness of the decisions, planned manoeuvres, and resulting trajectories. To counteract this, algorithms for motion planning should consider potential uncertainties in the underlying information and at the same time maximise their own process-related level of accuracy and robustness.

5.2.2 Methodology

Within this subtask of T3.5, IKA focuses on planning reasonable trajectories in a robust manner mainly by using as much information as possible from different sources of information and by combining knowledge- and data-driven AI in the motion planning system.

The implemented system consists of a sequential combination of a Deep-Learning based approach for generating an initial trajectory and a knowledge-based approach that investigates and adapts the planned trajectory based on various rules, e.g. on drivability due to driving dynamics.

5.2.3 Results and next steps

As illustrated in Figure 34 the data-driven approach for generating a trajectory is based on a Convolutional Neural Network architecture, that utilizes a Birds-Eye-View representation of the vehicle environment as input. On the other hand, the neural network outputs predictions for future vehicle states over a fixed time horizon, including time-discrete state variables such as the x- and y-position and velocity of the vehicle. Training data are derived from the nuPlan dataset [35].

Figure 34: Visualized input representation and predicted trajectory of the implemented CNN-based behaviour generation module.

Before the trajectory is provided to the lower-level controllers, it is verified through another software module in a rule-based manner. On the one hand, this module ensures drivability, considering the physical driving constraints of a vehicle, and additionally checks the proposed trajectory according to rudimentary rules, such as not leaving the lane. If necessary, the trajectory can be adjusted accordingly, or a safe manoeuvre can be initiated. Moreover, through the continuous evaluation of the ML-based trajectory suggestion, scenarios and situations can be identified in which the data-driven approach underperforms. This could be roundabout scenarios, that are currently not part of the training data for example. By identifying these scenarios, a targeted retraining of the neural network can be triggered to enhance its accuracy and robustness especially in these scenarios.

5.3 Generating trajectories for critical driving scenarios

5.3.1 Introduction

One of the key risks in planning trajectories for autonomous mobility arises when the cars must decide in critical driving scenarios, especially if it is likely to result in an accident. The challenge lies in training deep-learning models for this task, as most of the current open-source datasets do not contain these scenarios.

5.3.2 Methodology

Recreating critical driving scenarios in real-life, e.g., for jaywalking, lane cutting etc., can be risky as well as expensive. Hence, such scenarios are mostly simulated and tested on driving simulators such as CARLA. However, the creation of such artificial scenarios is typically time-consuming and mostly fails to reflect edge cases. An alternate approach, which is largely unexplored, is to use deep-learning methods to learn the patterns from real-world accidents and to use them to simulate critical driving scenarios.

Figure 35: STRIVE [36]

The framework “STRIVE” proposed by NVIDIA [36] simulates such trajectories, as shown in Figure 35, The Adversary refers to the simulated trajectory of the non-ego vehicle which causes a critical driving scenario. In our work we plan to replace the prior distribution in this framework with our model, so that the newly simulated trajectories represent more real-world vehicle trajectories in critical/accident-prone scenarios.

5.3.3 Results and next steps

To achieve this objective, BUW uses dashcam videos, part of the open-source YouTube dataset, which record an on-road accident or a near accident scenario to train a deep-learning model to learn vehicle-trajectories in such critical scenarios. This model will then be used to simulate the trajectories of non-ego vehicles at random to create critical driving scenarios. Thus, we will have an environment where the ego-vehicle can be trained to detect, avoid, and re-plan its trajectories in such risky scenarios.

5.4 Situation awareness: Competence, context, and risk

5.4.1 Introduction

One of the biggest challenges for trustworthy AI is the mismatch between a data-driven AI algorithm (in this case the trajectory planner) that works on the sub-symbolic (statistical) level, and the specification of its requirements and its Operational Design Domain (ODD), that are defined on the symbolic level (representing objects in the world and their relationships). The performance on the training/testing set of an AI algorithm shows its trustworthiness on a statistical level. Essentially, the ODD is defined by the examples in the test set on which the algorithm performed well enough. However, such a statistical ODD description is not sufficient to judge whether the system meets its requirements that were defined on the symbolic level (i.e., successfully plan a trajectory on intersections in an urban environment in Germany). To this end, TNO has developed a situation

awareness module that determines the trustworthiness of an AI system on the symbolic level. We have applied this to the trajectory planner described in Sec 16.18.

An important aspect of situation awareness is context-dependent competence: is the system capable of performing according to its requirements in the current context? A context comprises a situation combined with the expected behaviour of the system in that situation. The higher the competence in a certain context, the higher the expected performance of the planner. Competence is related to experience. Situations and environments that have been encountered more frequently and in greater variety can be handled with more competence than their unfamiliar counterparts. To make statements about the competence within a given situation, comparisons to previously experienced contexts can be made to find similar examples on which to base the decision-making process. The more examples exist that are like the present context, and the closer their resemblance, the higher the expected competence and performance within the current context will be. On the other hand, when the context is completely different from all situations encountered before, the competence will be low, meaning that the performance of the planner might not be trustworthy. Note that this does not mean the actual performance of the planner is incorrect in never encountered situations, only that it might not be as reliable as in other situations.

5.4.2 Methodology

We use a knowledge graph database to model contexts on the symbolic level. This type of database is designed to model knowledge using a graph structure, which contains nodes, edges, attributes, and labels, and focuses on modelling the relationships between entities. An example can be seen in Figure 36. Entities can be represented in a graph using nodes (also called vertices). Each node is equipped with a collection of labels and attributes to distinguish it from other nodes within the graph. Relationships between nodes are modelled using edges, with each edge connecting a pair of vertices. Like nodes, edges can also be distinguished using labels and attributes. Labels are used to identify types of nodes/edges, whereas attributes can be used to distinguish between nodes and edges that share a label.

Figure 36: Example of a knowledge graph representing the context.

We have encoded the dataset that the trajectory planner has been trained on into the knowledge graph, using an ontology of urban driving. This way, we elevate the sub-symbolic description of the ODD to the symbolic level. This has several advantages:

- Competence estimation: we can define a measure of competence of the trajectory planner given the current context;
- Risk assessment: we can reason about the risk of the actions of the vehicle given the competence and the context;
- Providing explanation: we can ask the system for explanations about competence, context, and risk on the symbolic level.

For this deliverable, we focus on the first element, competence estimation. Using the sets of nodes, edges, labels, and attributes in the knowledge graph, we can model and compare contexts at the symbolic level. As the ego vehicle finds itself in a (new) situation, the context can be modelled as a knowledge graph and compared to contexts in the training set. Based on the level of similarity and the number of similar contexts that match the current context, we can then make statements about the competence of the planner and therefore its expected performance within the given context.

5.4.3 Results and next steps

Figure 37 shows an example for the computed similarity of two contexts modelled as knowledge graphs. The similarity computation assesses the overlap of both graphs in terms of nodes (including their labels and attributes) and edges (including edge directionality, labels, and attributes). The computed similarity for the graphs below is a result of the additional Crosswalk node and Lane node in

the first graph, as well as the difference in the turn type (right, left, or straight) attribute for one of the Connector nodes.

Figure 37: Similarity between two contexts

In this simplified example, only two contexts are compared for visualisation purposes. In practice, the current context is compared to all contexts in the training set (in other words, the ODD of the planner) to compute the level of competence.

Currently, the competence computation takes too long to run real-time in the vehicle. Thus, one of the next steps we will take is to improve the efficiency of this calculation. In addition, the competence value will be calibrated against the performance of the trajectory planner and integrated in the full architecture of the system.

5.5 Network level impact of introducing AVs

5.5.1 Introduction

UC4 AI-based Traffic Management (TM) focusses on the impact of AI-based Automated Vehicles (AVs) on the network level from a traffic management perspective, instead of focusing on the AI in a single vehicle. As mentioned in D1.2, UC4 envisions introducing AI-based AVs into a real-life urban traffic network. The accelerating development and increasing uptake of AVs strongly calls for the CCAM ecosystem to solve emerging and future challenges for users/participants.

UC4 AI-based TM predominantly takes a virtual approach over the two cycles of the Althena project to assess the interactions of AVs and non-AVs under different vehicle compositions. By using virtual microsimulation, we can study how introducing AVs into network influences overall traffic dynamics from a traffic management perspective, aiming to evaluate aspects of efficiency, safety, and sustainability.

Following the Althena explainable AI (XAI) approach, as written in D1.2, the study focusses on the concepts of trust and transparency. AVs need to trust third-party information to overcome certain edge cases, and understanding how AVs impact the traffic dynamics on the network level will increase transparency for road authorities with respect to implications of allowing AVs on their roads.

To understand the relation between trust and penetration grades of AVs, traffic needs to be simulated using several different compositions of vehicle types (e.g., AV-with-trust, AV-without-trust, non-AV, etc.). Microsimulation is the most appropriate way to do that, as is explained next.

5.5.2 Methodology

Microsimulation is employed to simulate traffic dynamics within a macroscopic network. This allows for the creation of various layouts and the reflection of real-life infrastructure. Traffic dynamics are calculated by iterating through small timesteps (usually 10 per second) and calculating the behaviour/action for each vehicle in the network for each timestep. Different behavioural models can be used, each with its own parameters, to emulate various types of driving behaviours. For example, it is possible to simulate a normal passenger car with a more conservative (i.e., slower acceleration, breaking and keeping more distance) or more aggressive behaviour (i.e., quicker to overtake vehicles). Similarly, the behavioural characteristics of an automated vehicle can be emulated. In addition, through a programmatic interface, it is possible to create edge cases and/or specific behaviours. This interface enables the implementation of specific scenarios that are especially challenging for AVs from a traffic management perspective.

Given the requirements (different networks, vehicle models, AV models, programmatic interface, and see [1]), MAPtm has conducted a review of available microsimulation software that enables the evaluation of macroscopic traffic scenarios. The most promising solutions are VISSIM and SUMO, which both have their advantages and disadvantages. For now, UC4 uses VISSIM¹ [37] to simulate macroscopic traffic networks.

Using simulation to assess trust

In the first cycle, UC4 applies VISSIM to assess the impact of AVs-with-trust or AVs-without-trust on a proof-of-concept network before implementing UC4 on a macroscopic traffic network. The following pragmatic states of VISSIM are used in the first cycle to simulate UC4.

VISSIM contains several sub-models, such as a car-following model, lane-changing model, lateral behaviour model, etc., to simulate complex and heterogenous driving behaviours. The trustworthiness of AVs as perceived by others (AVs and non-AVs), and hence their interactions, depend on the outcomes from the sub-models in VISSIM. The benchmark for desired behaviours in UC4 is based on a reference model of 100% non-AVs driving on a macroscopic urban network using the default driving behaviour parameters for car-following and lane changing from the Wiedermann 99 model.

Based on the AV logics created in the CoEXist [38] project, VISSIM has developed a set of AV models: AV rail safe, AV cautious, AV normal, and AV all-knowing. This set of AV models is derived from non-AV driving behaviours (Wiedermann 99) and specially featured parameters required to model AVs in VISSIM. UC4 uses default parameters of AVs cautious in VISSIM, which already imply extensive functionalities to model AV behaviours inclusively. According to the sensitivity analysis of UC4 in D5.2 [1], adapting the driving behaviour parameters is not needed in the first cycle of Athena.

The scenario timeline of UC4 is crucial for simulating and assessing the impact of trust by analysing results. Modelling such a complex UC 4 timeline with CCAM functions requires external interfacing. Thus, UC4 performs all simulations with the extended interface of VISSIM: COM (Component Object

¹ For the second cycle AITHENA might switch to SUMO which is an open-source alternative.

Model) interface. In this cycle, scripts written in python are used to enable the UC4 scenario timelines as designed. In the second cycle, other methods, such as drivermodel.dll and DrivingSimulator.dll might be suitable for building on the first cycle results of other use cases, i.e., UC 2 and 3.

Three different dimensions are defined to perform simulations: percentage of AV among all vehicles, percentage of AV-with-trust among AVs, and Level of Services (LOS). In the first cycle, the LOS is fixed to LOS A² [39]. The other two dimensions are varied to define the AV composition matrix. As the composition of Light Good Vehicles (LGV) and Heavy Good Vehicles (HGV) is fixed to 5% and 2% respectively in the first cycle, Table 3 presents the AV composition matrix with each combination of percentage of AV among all vehicles (incrementing interval of 25%) and percentage of AV-with-trust among AVs (incrementing interval of 25%). With this table, 25 vehicle mixes are defined and configured in the proof-of-concept simulation network in VISSIM. Depending on the results using these 25 vehicle mixes, additional (in-between) mixes can be used to better understand the sensitivity of the outcome given the vehicle mix.

Table 3: AV composition matrix.

Percentage of AV among all vehicles	Percentage of AV-with-trust among AVs					
	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%	
0%	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	
25%	0-23	6-17	12-12	17-6	23-0	
50%	0-47	12-35	23-23	35-12	47-0	
75%	0-70	17-52	35-35	52-17	70-0	
100%	0-93	23-70	47-47	70-23	93-0	

Prerequisites

Because of the exponential rate of AV technology development, visualising and evaluating the impact of AVs on a simulation network is both complex and dynamic. The following prerequisites are specified and applied to all simulations.

- The chosen urban intersections network is fully covered by a homogeneous Operational Design Domain (ODD) for fully automated vehicles, except for a few road segments which undergo ODD deterioration under certain corner/edge cases.
- The reference model reflects the realistic traffic behaviours of the live urban intersections network in current operating conditions of the traffic system. The traffic system is active to detect vehicle breakdown instantly and sent out TM measure with no latency.
- The current traffic system consists of mostly non-AVs driven by human drivers. The reference model is derived from non-AVs of competent human driver behaviours that respect the rules of the road (ROTRs), yet intelligent enough to ignore ROTR to overcome extenuating circumstances in the interests of transport network optimisation.
- In most circumstances, AVs are expected to act like a human-driven vehicle. However, the driving behaviour parameters of AVs are different from that of non-AVs in the following aspects:
 - Non-AV is implicitly stochastic in VISSIM to simulate the distribution of human behaviours. Contrarily, AV are deterministic regarding values such as the risk acceptance, ability to estimate distance and speed difference, and the precision when operating the throttle and

² To achieve a functional proof-of-concept and exclude server congestion, i.e. congestion upstream propagation creating gridlock, LOS A is calibrated to 1200 vehicles per hour on link 1 (incident link) and 300 vehicles per hour on link 2 (opposite direction link where vehicles overtaking break-down vehicle manoeuvres take place).

braking pedals. As a result, the behaviour of AVs is homogeneous (e.g. they accelerate/decelerate the same/very similar way).

- In the second cycle, an increase in acceleration and small headways can be simulated using the AV all-knowing model. That model considers CCAM functions of AV which enables more efficient behaviours that are impossible or too dangerous for human drivers.

5.5.3 UC4 design

To model AVs and non-AVs on an urban network, a heuristic approach of building a proof-of-concept was taken in the UC4 design phase to realise the featured functionalities of AVs overcoming an incident blockage using the opposite lane. To do so, the schematic design delineates the situation where a vehicle breakdown incident happens on a single-lane urban road in Figure 38. The single-lane, two-direction road is separated with solid line. On the one hand, the non-AVs show reference behaviours one by one, that they stop behind the breakdown vehicle, observe the oncoming traffic, and take over by crossing the solid line (across and back) safely. On the other hand, AVs are likely to stop behind the breakdown vehicle and show undesired cautious behaviours in this challenging scenario. UC4 proof-of concept provides solutions via broadcasting TM message instantly with no latency.

Figure 38: Schematic design of a vehicle breakdown incident on single-lane urban road.

Figure 39 below shows a snapshot of the proof-of-concept network in VISSIM. The blue passenger car with a red circle is the breakdown vehicle. When the breakdown incident happens, the active traffic management system detects the incident and begins to broadcast TM messages. If an AV is an AV-with-trust, it overtakes using opposite direction lane as advised by the TM messages; If an AV is an AV-without-trust, it stops for 10 seconds until its backup system (e.g., handover, remote control, remote guidance, etc.) performs the overtaking manoeuvre. The turquoise passenger car is an AV-with-trust overtaking the breakdown vehicle while the following passenger cars are non-AVs that perform the overtaking by themselves.

Figure 39: A snapshot example of UC4 Proof-of-concept at runtime.

Figure 40: UC4 algorithm flowchart according to the incident timeline.

The core features of the proof-of-concept are depicted by the UC4 algorithm flowchart, shown in Figure 40 above. Upon entry of the flowchart, each step is executed chronologically aiming for simulating individual vehicle behaviours towards the incident, the vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-infrastructure (TM) interactions and the impact of such behaviours and interactions on the network level. The control statements in Figure 40 raise questions which implement the logical decision-making processes of AVs, other vehicles, and TM system. The flowchart amplifies the timeline around the incident when the overtaking using opposite lane manoeuvres happen intensively. Once the incident duration of 590 seconds has passed, the breakdown vehicle starts driving again and exits the network. The rest of the simulation is expected to evolve in a straightforward, predictable way.

A python script containing the above UC4 algorithm was created to perform each simulation as designed using the VISSIM COM interface. The simulation results are saved at runtime.

5.5.4 Results and next steps

Results

In the proof-of-concept, one simulation run lasts two hours with the first half hour warming up and the last half hour cooling down. At 45 minutes, a vehicle breakdown incident occurs on the eastbound link. The incident lasts for 590 seconds, during which the breakdown vehicle is stopped and blocks the

eastbound single-lane urban road. One by one, the following vehicles react as indicated in the UC4 algorithm flowchart Figure 40. Just before the 55-minute timestamp, the breakdown vehicle is moving on and the traffic returns to normal. The proof-of-concept was achievable.

To account for stochastic variations, each simulation of the same dimension (i.e., a fixed vehicle mix with a certain percentage of AVs and a certain percentage of AV-with-trust under a fixed LOS) is run 10 times, while the seed is increased by 78 with each iteration starting at 42. The total vehicle delay is exported from VISSIM for retrieving the two hours simulation results. Since we have 25 variations and 250 runs in total, scripting was created to automatically process and calculate the results. The results of the KPI — total vehicle delays are explained in D5.2.

Figure 41: UC4 schematic design for the second cycle of Althena.

After the successful completion of UC4 PoC, we looked for a real-world intersection where the PoC can be integrated into. A schematic design of such an intersection is depicted above in Figure 41. The red vehicle has a breakdown incident on the single-lane approach to the intersection. The following vehicles need to follow the incident timeline according to Figure 40.

Next steps

The next step in the second cycle is to build and realise the UC4 PoC on a single intersection network. Following that, the intersection with a vehicle breakdown incident will be upscaled to a macroscopic network (see Figure 42).

Figure 42: Simulation(left) and geographic (right) network overview of UC4 – part of Heemstede

In addition to upscaling the network, the following steps are considered:

- Identify the AV behaviour and possibly edge cases from the other Athena use cases. Use those to mirror identified behaviours and/or edge cases in the microsimulation.
- Through desk research, we can identify additional edge cases and implement these once or multiple times in microsimulations.
- We can explore the use of SUMO microsimulation software in addition to or instead of VISSIM. SUMO is open source and available to more partners. This makes it easier to collaborate and/or distribute the work. In addition, since it is open source, there are less limitations to implement adaptations to enable specific AV behaviours and/or edge case situations.

6 CONCLUSIONS

D3.2 provides first initial overview of the AI algorithms developed in Althena, with a focus on the 3 main areas as defined in the Althena architecture in Figure 1: perception, situation awareness / understanding and decision-making.

As also the model cards as part of the ML framework (as earlier described in D3.1 [2]) that were developed in T3.1 are a continuous development, this deliverable also provided a short update on those

For each of the algorithms, background (introduction), a methodology and preliminary results are given. Since this deliverable focuses mainly on the development and explanation of the methodology used in the development of the algorithms, the results are only briefly described. For more detailed results and evaluation linked also to the use cases, a more detailed evaluation is provided in deliverable D5.2 [1]. One exception in this case, is use case UC2.2; since this use case is strongly linked to all four main development tasks of WP3 (T3.2 – T3.5) with many partners collaborating and it has already been in full development since the early beginnings of the project.

As this deliverable marks the end of the first development cycle, the developments will continue in the next cycle. D3.2 will be followed-up by an updated deliverable D3.3 in M32 (30 June 2025) with the second iteration of the AI algorithms, based on the integration and testing within the use cases as described in WP5.

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